

Package ‘prior3D’

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Type Package

Title 3D prioritization algorithm

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Description 3D prioritization algorithm.

Imports prioritizr (>= 8.0.3),
terra (>= 1.7.71),
maps (>= 3.4.2),
highs (>= 0.1.10),
viridis (>= 0.6.5),
readxl (>= 1.4.3),
tools (>= 4.4.0),
rasterdiv (>= 0.3.4),
geodiv,
methods,
stats,
utils,
graphics

Suggests knitr,
gurobi (>= 11.0.1),
slam (>= 0.1.50),
markdown,
rmarkdown,
roxygen2

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Depends R (>= 2.10)

VignetteBuilder knitr

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biodiv_df	<i>Example biodiversity data.frame</i>
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Description

Example biodiversity data.frame

Usage

```
data(biodiv_df)
```

Details

Example of input biodiv_df used for functions.

Value

data.frame object with information about features.

Examples

```
## Not run:
data(biodiv_df)
head(biodiv_df)

## End(Not run)
```

coherence	<i>Coherence metrics</i>
-----------	--------------------------

Description

Coherence metrics

Usage

```
coherence(x, w, metric = "sa", normalize = TRUE, plot = TRUE, addlines = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

x	Output of Compare_2D_3D function.
w	Integer indicating square window dimensions.
metric	Cohension metric to use. It must be one of "sa", "sku" and "rao"
normalize	If TRUE, then sum of solutions is normalized at a [0, 1] scale.
plot	If TRUE, then coherence maps are plotted.
addlines	If TRUE, then border lines from <code>maps::map</code> are plotted.
...	Further arguments passed in function, based on metric choice. See more in Details.

Details

"sa" and "sku" are derived from `geodiv::focal_metrics` and in `ellipsis(...)` further arguments of `geodiv::focal_metrics` are passed.

`metric = "rao"` is derived from `rasterdiv::paRao` and in `ellipsis(...)` further arguments of `rasterdiv::paRao` are passed.

References

Rocchini, Duccio, Matteo Marcantonio, Daniele Da Re, Giovanni Bacaro, Enrico Feoli, Giles Foody, Reinhard Furrer, et al. 2021. "From zero to infinity: Minimum to maximum diversity of the planet by spatio-parametric Rao's quadratic entropy." *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 30 (5): 2315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13270>.

Rocchini, Duccio, Elisa Thouverai, Matteo Marcantonio, Martina Iannacito, Daniele Da Re, Michele Torresani, Giovanni Bacaro, et al. 2021. "rasterdiv - An Information Theory tailored R package for measuring ecosystem heterogeneity from space: To the origin and back." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 12 (6): 2195. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13583>.

Smith, Annie C., Phoebe Zarnetske, Kyla Dahlin, Adam Wilson, and Andrew Latimer. 2023. *Geodiv: Methods for Calculating Gradient Surface Metrics*. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=geodiv>.

Becker OScbRA, Minka ARWRvbRBEbTP, Deckmyn. A (2023). *maps: Draw Geographical Maps*. R package version 3.4.2, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=maps>

See Also

[Compare_2D_3D](#)

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

out_2D_3D <- Compare_2D_3D(biodiv_raster = biodiv_raster,
                           depth_raster = depth_raster,
                           breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                           biodiv_df = biodiv_df,
                           budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                           budget_weights = "richness",
                           threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                           portfolio = "gap",
                           portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

coherence(out_2D_3D, w = 3, metric = "sa")
coherence(out_2D_3D, w = 3, metric = "sku")
coherence(out_2D_3D, w = 3, metric = "rao")

## End(Not run)
```

Compare_2D_3D

Compare 2D vs 3D prioritization algorithms

Description

Compare 2D vs 3D prioritization algorithms

Usage

```
Compare_2D_3D(biodiv_raster, depth_raster, breaks, biodiv_df, val_depth_range = TRUE,
              priority_weights = NULL, budget_percents = seq(0,1,0.1), budget_weights = "equal",
              penalty = 0, edge_factor = 0.5, gap = 0.1, threads = 1L, sep_priority_weights = ",",
              portfolio = "gap", portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10, pool_gap = 0.1),
              sep_biodiv_df = ",", locked_in_raster = NULL, locked_out_raster = NULL, verbose = FALSE)
```

Arguments

biodiv_raster	SpatRaster object or folder path with 2D feature distributions as layers.
depth_raster	SpatRaster object or file path with elevation/bathymetric map.
breaks	Numeric vector defining the range of depth layers to use.
biodiv_df	data.frame or a file path (CSV, TXT, XLS, or XLSX) containing additional information about biodiversity features.
val_depth_range	No correction of the splitted 3D distributions based on depth range of the biodiversity features ("min_z" and "max_z" from biodiv_df) is needed.
priority_weights	data.frame object or file path (CSV, TXT, XLS, or XLSX) containing group names of biodiversity features in the first column and corresponding group weights in the second column. This data.frame attributes distinct prioritization weights to different biodiversity features or groups of features.

budget_percents	Numeric value [0, 1] or vector containing budget percentages to use. The default is <code>seq(0, 1, 0.1)</code> .
budget_weights	Numeric weight vector for budget_percents allocation among depth levels. Otherwise it can be a string with one of the choices "equal", "area" or "richness". Alternatively, it can be a numerical vector with custom weights corresponding to each depth layer, where the first value corresponds to the surface and last one corresponds to the bottom of the sea. The weights are normalized if their sum exceeds 1. If not specified, an equal distribution of budget among depth levels is used, as the default.
penalty	Numeric penalty applied to each depth zone, as defined in the <code>prioritizr::add_boundary_penalties</code> .
edge_factor	Numeric edge factor applied to each depth zone, as defined in the <code>prioritizr::add_boundary_penalties</code> .
gap	The optimality gap for the solver, as defined in the prioritizr package. The default gap is 0.1.
threads	The number of solver threads to be used. The default is 1.
sep_priority_weights	Separator used in priority_weights file, if priority_weights is in path format.
portfolio	The portfolio to be used, choosing between "extra", "gap", "cuts" and "shuffle" portfolios. The default is "gap". <code>portfolio=""</code> indicates that no portfolio is used. For more about portfolios see prioritizr .
portfolio_opts	The prioritizr portfolio options to be used.
sep_biodiv_df	Separator used in biodiv_df file, if biodiv_df is in path format.
locked_in_raster	An optional locked_in_raster SpatRaster to be used. Note that these areas are considered as zero-cost.
locked_out_raster	An optional locked_out_raster SpatRaster to be used. Note that these areas are excluded from the solution.
verbose	If <code>verbose = TRUE</code> , then solver messages are printed as well. The default is <code>FALSE</code> .

Details

To facilitate comparisons between 3D and 2D approaches, the `compare_2D_3D()` function is provided in the package. This function enables users to conduct all steps of the analysis (data generation, setting and solving the optimization problem and producing outputs), by executing both 2D and 3D approaches, with similar settings, that facilitate comparisons. The function generates corresponding maps and graphs for both approaches.

The `split_rast` function is used to convert 2D distributions of biodiversity features (rasters) into a 3D format.

Here the `biodiv_df` can have the following column names (independently of their order and any other names are ignored):

- "species_name": **Mandatory** column with the feature names, which must be the same with `biodiv_raster`.
- "pelagic": **Mandatory** column about the features' behaviour. `TRUE` means that this feature is pelagic and `FALSE` means that this feature is benthic.

- "min_z": **Optional** column about the minimum vertical range of features. NA values are translated as unlimited upward feature movement.
- "max_z": **Optional** column about the maximum vertical range of features. NA values are translated as unlimited downward feature movement.
- "group": **Optional** column with the group weights names.

Except from `biodiv_df`, an additional `data.frame` object can also be used for defining group weights, named `priority_weights`. If used, this `data.frame` object must have two columns:

- "group": **Mandatory** column with the group weights names.
- "weight": **Mandatory** column with the group weights.

In case that no feature weights are desired, then `priority_weights` can be kept to `NULL`.

`breaks` must be in correspondance to `depth_raster` file. For example, if `depth_raster` has range `[10, -3000]`, then a `breaks` vector of `c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf)` will create depth levels `[0, -40]`, `(-40, -200]`, `(-200, -2000]`, `(-2000, -∞)` and set to NA cells with values greater than 0.

If `val_depth_range = TRUE` (default), then no correction is done and the depth range of the biodiversity features is derived from the corresponding feature distribution raster and so "min_z" and "max_z" are ignored. If `val_depth_range = FALSE`, then the function uses the minimum and maximum depth information provided in the `biodiv_df`, so as to remove feature occurrences outside their expected range.

`budget_percents`: Budget reflects the desired level of protection to be modeled. It ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating no resources available for protection, while 1 signifies resources sufficient to protect the entire study area. Typically, setting a budget of 0.3 corresponds to the 30% conservation target (i.e. 30% of the total area set aside for conservation). Users also have the flexibility to define multiple budget levels using a vector, allowing for the exploration of various protection scenarios. For instance, a vector like `c(0.1, 0.3, 0.5)` represents three scenarios where 10%, 30%, and 50% of the study area are designated for protection.

`budget_weights`: The **Compare_2D_3D** function allows users to specify how the budget is distributed among depth levels. Three allocation methods are available:

1. Equal Distribution: Allocates an equal share of the budget to each depth level (`budget_weights = "equal"`).
2. Proportional to Area: Allocates budget based on the spatial extent of each depth level (`budget_weights = "area"`).
3. Proportional to Species Richness: Prioritizes budget allocation to depth levels with higher species diversity (number of species). (`budget_weights = "richness"`)

Otherwise, it can be a numeric vector with length equal to the number of depth levels, where each number indicates the budget share per depth level.

The solver used for solving the prioritization problems is the best available on the computer, following the solver hierarchy of **prioritizr**.

Value

A list containing the following objects (non-referenced are identical to the input ones):

- `split_features`: output of `split_rast`
- `solution3D`: list with 3D solution per budget percentage
- `absolute_held3D`: `absolute_held` for 3D solutions (see `evaluate_3D`)
- `overall_held3D`: `overall_held` for 3D solutions (see `evaluate_3D`)


```

        portfolio = "gap",
        portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot = "all", add_lines=TRUE)

# Arbitrary random weights
priority_weights <- data.frame(c("A", "B", "C"), c(0.001, 1000, 1))
names(priority_weights) <- c("group", "weight")
biodiv_df$group <- rep(c("A", "B", "C"), length.out=20)
out_2D_3D <- Compare_2D_3D(biodiv_raster = biodiv_raster,
                          depth_raster = depth_raster,
                          breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                          biodiv_df = biodiv_df,
                          priority_weights = priority_weights,
                          budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                          budget_weights = "richness",
                          threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                          portfolio = "gap",
                          portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot = "all", add_lines=TRUE)

## End(Not run)

```

evaluate_3D

Evaluate prioritization solution over 3D feature distributions

Description

Evaluate prioritization solution over 3D feature distributions.

Usage

```
evaluate_3D(solution, split_features)
```

Arguments

<code>solution</code>	prioritization solution SpatRaster object.
<code>split_features</code>	A list of SpatRaster objects representing depth zones, where each element corresponds to a different depth level, ranging from surface to the bottom of the sea. The function uses the output of the <code>split_rast</code> function, but other multilevel (3D) distribution data that conform to this structure is also acceptable. First list element corresponds to the shallowest distribution and the last list element to the deepest one.

Details

This function evaluates a prioritization solution over 3D feature distributions, by estimating the relative and overall percentages of features under protection, as designated by the prioritization solution.

Value

A list containing the following evaluation metrics:

- `relative_held_raw`: relative percentage under protection per feature and per depth level
- `relative_held`: mean percentage under protection of all features per depth level
- `overall_held`: overall percentage under protection per feature
- `overall_available`: relative percentage under protection per feature and per depth level, over total amount of each feature
- `depth_overall_available`: averages of `overall_available` per depth
- `absolute_held`: absolute value per feature and per depth under protection
- `total_amount`: absolute value per feature and depth level

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

# You can split features' 2D distributions into 3D ones and then run only 3D analysis
split_features <- split_rast(biodiv_raster,
                             depth_raster,
                             breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                             biodiv_df)

out_3D <- prioritize_3D(split_features = split_features,
                       depth_raster = depth_raster,
                       breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                       budget_percents = 0.3,
                       budget_weights = "richness",
                       threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                       portfolio = "gap",
                       portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

evaluate_3D(out_3D$solution3D$budget0.3, split_features)

## End(Not run)
```

`get_biodiv_raster` *Example biodiversity raster*

Description

Example biodiversity raster

Usage

```
get_biodiv_raster()
```

Details

Example of input `biodiv_raster` used for functions.

Value

SpatRaster object with distribution of features.

References

Kaschner, K., Kesner-Reyes, K., Garilao, C., Segschneider, J., Rius-Barile, J., Rees, T., & Froese, R. (2019). AquaMaps: Predicted range maps for aquatic species. <https://www.aquamaps.org>

Examples

```
## Not run:  
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()  
terra::plot(biodiv_raster[[1:4]])  
  
## End(Not run)
```

get_depth_raster	<i>Example depth raster</i>
------------------	-----------------------------

Description

Example depth raster

Usage

```
get_depth_raster()
```

Details

Example of input depth_df object for functions.

Value

SpatRaster object with depth levels for Mediterranean.

References

GEBCO Compilation Group. (2021). GEBCO 2021 Grid. <https://doi.org/10.5285/c6612cbe-50b3-0cff-e053-6c86abc09f8f>

Examples

```
## Not run:  
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()  
terra::plot(depth_raster)  
  
## End(Not run)
```

get_rast	<i>Read multiple rast files</i>
----------	---------------------------------

Description

Read multiple rast files contained in a folder path. Raster files must have either .asc or .tif extension.

Usage

```
get_rast(path)
```

Arguments

path	Path string of folder containing rast files.
------	--

Value

A SpatRaster object.

Examples

```
## Not run:
feature_folder <- system.file("get_rast_example", package="prior3D")
get_rast(feature_folder)

## End(Not run)
```

plot_3D	<i>Plot output of prioritize_3D</i>
---------	---

Description

Plot summarized output of [prioritize_3D](#)

Usage

```
plot_3D(x, to_plot = "all", add_lines = TRUE)
```

Arguments

x	Output of prioritize_3D .
to_plot	Any of "maps", "relative_held" or "all". The default is "all". See more in Details.
add_lines	If TRUE, then border lines from maps::map are plotted as well.

Details

This function plots the summarized output of `prioritize_3D` for all the selected budgets. The produced plot can contain information about:

- "maps": produced maps normalized at a $[0, 1]$ scale.
- "relative_held": percentage of protection for all features per depth level.
- "all": both "maps" and "relative_held".

Value

A plot.

References

Becker, R.A., Wilks, A.R., Brownrigg, R., & Minka, T.P. (2023). maps: Draw Geographical Maps. R package version 3.4.2, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=maps>

See Also

`prioritize_3D`

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

# You can split features' 2D distributions into 3D ones and then run only 3D analysis
split_features <- split_rast(biodiv_raster,
                             depth_raster,
                             breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                             biodiv_df,
                             val_depth_range=TRUE)

out_3D <- prioritize_3D(split_features = split_features,
                       depth_raster = depth_raster,
                       breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                       biodiv_df = biodiv_df,
                       priority_weights = NULL, #priority_weights,
                       budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                       budget_weights = "equal",
                       penalty = 0,
                       edge_factor = 0.5,
                       gap = 0.1,
                       threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                       sep_priority_weights = "",
                       portfolio = "gap",
                       portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10),
                       sep_biodiv_df = "",
                       locked_in_raster = NULL,
                       locked_out_raster = NULL)

plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=FALSE)
plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=TRUE)
```

```
plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="maps", add_lines=TRUE)
plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="relative_held", add_lines=TRUE)

## End(Not run)
```

plot_Compare_2D_3D *Plot output of [Compare_2D_3D](#)*

Description

Plot summarized output of [Compare_2D_3D](#)

Usage

```
plot_Compare_2D_3D(x, to_plot = "all", add_lines = TRUE)
```

Arguments

x	Output of Compare_2D_3D .
to_plot	Any of "maps", "relative_held" or "all". The default is "all". See more in Details.
add_lines	If TRUE, then border lines from maps::map are plotted as well.

Details

This function plots the summarized output of [Compare_2D_3D](#) for all selected budgets. The produced plot can contain information about:

- "maps": produced maps normalized at a [0, 1] scale.
- "relative_held": percentage of protection for all features per depth level.
- "all": both "maps" and "relative_held".

Value

A plot.

References

Becker, R. A., Wilks, A. R., Brownrigg, R., & Minka, T. P. (2023). maps: Draw Geographical Maps. R package version 3.4.2, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=maps>

See Also

[Compare_2D_3D](#)

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

out_2D_3D <- Compare_2D_3D(biodiv_raster = biodiv_raster,
                           depth_raster = depth_raster,
                           breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                           biodiv_df = biodiv_df,
                           budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                           budget_weights = "richness",
                           threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                           portfolio = "gap",
                           portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=FALSE)
plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=TRUE)
plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot="maps", add_lines=TRUE)
plot_Compare_2D_3D(out_2D_3D, to_plot="relative_held", add_lines=TRUE)

## End(Not run)
```

plot_sumrast

Plot sum list of SpatRaster objects.

Description

Plot sum list of SpatRaster objects.

Usage

```
plot_sumrast(x, normalize = TRUE, add_lines = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

x	List of SpatRaster objects.
normalize	If TRUE, then sum of solutions is normalized at a [0, 1] scale.
add_lines	If TRUE, then border lines from maps::map are plotted as well.
...	Further arguments passed to terra::plot

Value

A plot.

See Also

[sumrast](#)

Examples

```
## Not run:
set.seed(42)
x <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.2), nrow=10))
y <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.8), nrow=10))
plot_sumrast(list(x, y), add_lines = FALSE)

## End(Not run)
```

prioritize_3D

*3D prioritization algorithm***Description**

3D prioritization algorithm

Usage

```
prioritize_3D(split_features, depth_raster, breaks, biodiv_df = NULL,
priority_weights = NULL, budget_percents = seq(0,1,0.1), budget_weights = "equal",
penalty = 0, edge_factor = 0.5, gap = 0.1, threads = 1L, sep_priority_weights = ",",
portfolio = "gap", portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10, pool_gap = 0.1),
sep_biodiv_df = ",", locked_in_raster = NULL, locked_out_raster = NULL, verbose = FALSE)
```

Arguments

- split_features** list of SpatRaster objects representing depth zones, where each element corresponds to a different depth level, ranging from surface to the bottom of the sea. The function uses the output of the `split_rast` function, but other multilevel (3D) distribution data that conform to this structure is also acceptable. First list element corresponds to the shallowest distribution and the last list element to the deepest one.
- depth_raster** SpatRaster object or file path with elevation/bathymetric map.
- breaks** Numeric vector defining the range of depth layers to use.
- biodiv_df** data.frame or a file path (CSV, TXT, XLS, or XLSX) containing additional information about biodiversity features.
- priority_weights** data.frame object or file path (CSV, TXT, XLS, or XLSX) containing group names of biodiversity features in the first column and corresponding group weights in the second column. This data.frame attributes distinct prioritization weights to different biodiversity features or groups of features.
- budget_percents** Numeric value $[0, 1]$ or vector containing budget percentages to use. The default is `seq(0, 1, 0.1)`.
- budget_weights** Numeric weight vector for `budget_percents` allocation among depth levels. Otherwise it can be a string with one of the choices "equal", "area" or "richness". Alternatively, it can be a numerical vector with custom weights corresponding to each depth layer, where the first value corresponds to the surface and last one corresponds to the bottom of the sea. The weights are normalized if their sum exceeds 1. If not specified, an equal distribution of budget among depth levels is used, as the default.

penalty	A single numeric penalty applied to each depth zone, as defined in the <code>prioritizr::add_boundary_penalties</code> .
edge_factor	A single numeric edge factor applied to each depth zone, as defined in the <code>prioritizr::add_boundary_penalties</code> .
gap	The optimality gap for the solver, as defined in the prioritizr package. The default gap is 0.1.
threads	The number of solver threads to be used. The default is 1.
sep_priority_weights	Separator used in <code>priority_weights</code> file, if <code>priority_weights</code> is in path format.
portfolio	The portfolio to be used, choosing between "extra", "gap", "cuts" and "shuffle" portfolios. The default is "gap". <code>portfolio=""</code> indicates that no portfolio is used. For more about portfolios see prioritizr .
portfolio_opts	The prioritizr portfolio options to be used.
sep_biodiv_df	Separator used in <code>biodiv_df</code> file, if <code>biodiv_df</code> is in path format.
locked_in_raster	An optional <code>locked_in_raster</code> <code>SpatRaster</code> to be used. Note that these areas are considered as zero-cost.
locked_out_raster	An optional <code>locked_out_raster</code> <code>SpatRaster</code> to be used. Note that these areas are excluded from the solution.
verbose	If <code>verbose = TRUE</code> , then solver messages are printed as well. The default is <code>FALSE</code> .

Details

This function is used to generate prioritization maps. Single budget settings (ex. `total_budget = 0.3`) produce standard maps, as typical Marxan outputs. Multiple budgets, by using a vector (ex. `c(0.1, 0.3, 0.5)`), result in cumulative (frequency) maps, illustrating areas selected by various budget levels. Although this output follows a different approach, it resembles to typical Zonation output maps.

The main reason for `biodiv_df` here is defining prioritization weights for features. In this package weights are defined per group of features (if needed). `biodiv_df` has mandatory column names (and any other names are ignored):

- "species_name": **Mandatory** column with the feature names, which must be the same with `split_rast`.
- "group": **Mandatory** column with the group weights names.

Except from `biodiv_df`, an additional `data.frame` object can also be used, named `priority_weights`. If used, this `data.frame` object must have two columns:

- "group": **Mandatory** column with the group weights names.
- "weight": **Mandatory** column with the group weights.

In case that no feature weights are desired, then `biodiv_df` and `priority_weights` can be both kept to `NULL`.

`breaks` must be in correspondance to `depth_raster` file. For example, if `depth_raster` has range `[10, -3000]`, then a `breaks` vector of `c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf)` will create depth levels `[0, -40]`, `(-40, -200]`, `(-200, -2000]`, `(-2000, -∞)` and set to `NA` cells with values greater than 10.

`budget_percents`: Budget reflects the desired level of protection to be modeled. It ranges from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating no resources available for protection, while 1 signifies resources sufficient to

protect the entire study area. Typically, setting a budget of 0.3 corresponds to the 30% conservation target (i.e. 30% of the total area set aside for conservation). Users also have the flexibility to define multiple budget levels using a vector, allowing for the exploration of various protection scenarios. For instance, a vector like $c(0.1, 0.3, 0.5)$ represents three scenarios where 10%, 30%, and 50% of the study area are designated for protection.

`budget_weights`: The **prioritize_3D** function allows users to specify how the budget is distributed among depth levels. Three allocation methods are available:

1. Equal Distribution: Allocates an equal share of the budget to each depth level (`budget_weights = "equal"`).
2. Proportional to Area: Allocates budget based on the spatial extent of each depth level (`budget_weights = "area"`).
3. Proportional to Species Richness: Prioritizes budget allocation to depth levels with higher species diversity (number of species) (`budget_weights = "richness"`).

Otherwise, it can be a numeric vector with length equal to the number of depth levels, where each number indicates the budget share per depth level.

The solver used for solving the prioritization problems is the best available on the computer, following the solver hierarchy of **prioritizr**.

Value

A list containing the following objects (non-referenced are identical to the input ones):

- `solution3D`: list with 3D solution per budget percentage
- `absolute_held3D`: `absolute_held` for 3D solutions (see [evaluate_3D](#))
- `overall_held3D`: `overall_held` for 3D solutions (see [evaluate_3D](#))
- `relative_helds3D`: `relative_held` for 3D solutions (see [evaluate_3D](#))
- `mean_overall_helds3D`: `base::mean` of `overall_held` for 3D solution (see [evaluate_3D](#)) per budget
- `sd_overall_helds3D`: `base::sd` of `overall_held` for 3D solution (see [evaluate_3D](#)) per budget
- `depth_overall_available3D`: `depth_overall_available` for 3D solutions (see [evaluate_3D](#))

References

Hanson, Jeffrey O, Richard Schuster, Nina Morrell, Matthew Strimas-Mackey, Brandon P M Edwards, Matthew E Watts, Peter Arcese, Joseph Bennett, and Hugh P Possingham. 2024. `prioritizr`: Systematic Conservation Prioritization in R. <https://prioritizr.net>.

Lehtomäki, Joonas (2016). Comparing prioritization methods, 21 June. Available at: <https://rpubs.com/jlehtoma/priocomp> (Accessed 1 June 2024).

See Also

[evaluate_3D](#), [terra_jaccard](#), [plot_3D](#)

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

# You can split features' 2D distributions into 3D ones and then run only 3D analysis
split_features <- split_rast(biodiv_raster,
                            depth_raster,
                            breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                            biodiv_df)

out_3D <- prioritize_3D(split_features = split_features,
                       depth_raster = depth_raster,
                       breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                       budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                       budget_weights = "richness",
                       threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                       portfolio = "gap",
                       portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=TRUE)

# Arbitrary random weights
priority_weights <- data.frame(c("A", "B", "C"), c(0.001, 1000, 1))
names(priority_weights) <- c("group", "weight")
biodiv_df$group <- rep(c("A", "B", "C"), length.out=20)
out_3D <- prioritize_3D(split_features = split_features,
                       depth_raster = depth_raster,
                       biodiv_df = biodiv_df,
                       priority_weights = priority_weights,
                       breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
                       budget_percents = seq(0, 1, 0.1),
                       budget_weights = "richness",
                       threads = parallel::detectCores(),
                       portfolio = "gap",
                       portfolio_opts = list(number_solutions = 10))

plot_3D(out_3D, to_plot="all", add_lines=TRUE)

## End(Not run)
```

split_rast

Split 2D feature distributions into 3D ones

Description

Split 2D feature distributions into 3D ones

Usage

```
split_rast(biodiv_raster, depth_raster, breaks, biodiv_df, val_depth_range=TRUE,
           sep_biodiv_df=",")
```

Arguments

biodiv_raster	SpatRaster object or folder path with 2D feature distributions as layers.
depth_raster	SpatRaster object or file path with elevation/bathymetric map.
breaks	Numeric vector defining the range of depth layers to use.
biodiv_df	data.frame or a file path (CSV, TXT, XLS, or XLSX) containing additional information about biodiversity features.
val_depth_range	No correction of the splitted 3D distributions based on depth range of the biodiversity features ("min_z" and "max_z" from biodiv_df) is needed.
sep_biodiv_df	The separator used in biodiv_df file, if biodiv_df is in path format.

Details

This function is used to convert 2D distributions of biodiversity features (rasters) into a 3D format. Here the `biodiv_df` can have the following column names (independently of their order and any other names are ignored):

- "species_name": **Mandatory** column with the feature names, which must be the same with `biodiv_raster`.
- "pelagic": **Mandatory** column about the features' behaviour. TRUE means that this feature is pelagic and FALSE means that this feature is benthic.
- "min_z": **Optional** column about the minimum vertical range of features. NA values are translated as unlimited upward feature movement.
- "max_z": **Optional** column about the maximum vertical range of features. NA values are translated as unlimited downward feature movement.

`breaks` must be in correspondance to `depth_raster` file. For example, if `depth_raster` has range $[10, -3000]$, then a `breaks` vector of `c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf)` will create depth levels $[0, -40]$, $(-40, 200]$, $(-200, -2000]$, $(-2000, -\infty)$ and set to NA cells with values greater than 0.

If `val_depth_range = TRUE` (default), then no correction is done and the depth range of the biodiversity features is derived from the corresponding feature distribution raster and so "min_z" and "max_z" are ignored. If `val_depth_range = FALSE`, then the function uses the minimum and maximum depth information provided in the `biodiv_df`, so as to remove feature occurrences outside their expected range.

Value

A list containing species distributions for each bathymetric layer, that are necessary for further 3D analysis. List names are indicating the depth levels.

Examples

```
## Not run:
biodiv_raster <- get_biodiv_raster()
depth_raster <- get_depth_raster()
data(biodiv_df)

# You can split features' 2D distributions into 3D ones and then run only 3D analysis
split_features <- split_rast(biodiv_raster,
                             depth_raster,
                             breaks = c(0, -40, -200, -2000, -Inf),
```

```
biodiv_df)
```

```
## End(Not run)
```

sumrast	<i>Sum list of SpatRaster objects.</i>
---------	--

Description

Sum list of SpatRaster objects.

Usage

```
sumrast(x, normalize = TRUE)
```

Arguments

`x` List of SpatRaster objects.
`normalize` If TRUE, then sum of solutions is normalized at a $[0, 1]$ scale.

Value

A SpatRaster object.

See Also

[plot_sumrast](#)

Examples

```
## Not run:
set.seed(42)
x <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.2), nrow=10))
y <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.8), nrow=10))
sumrast(list(x, y))

## End(Not run)
```

terra_jaccard	<i>Jaccard similarity coefficient among two SpatRaster objects</i>
---------------	--

Description

Jaccard coefficient among two SpatRaster objects

Usage

```
terra_jaccard(x, y)
```

Arguments

x SpatRast object with binary values.
y SpatRast object with binary values.

Details

Jaccard similarity coefficient evaluates the percentage number equal to the intersection between two sets, divided by the size of the union of these sets.

Value

A numeric value [0, 1].

Examples

```
## Not run:  
set.seed(42)  
x <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.2), nrow=10))  
y <- terra::rast(matrix(rbinom(100, 1, 0.8), nrow=10))  
terra_jaccard(x, y)  
  
## End(Not run)
```

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